

CERAMIC COMPOSITES: DESIGN, MANUFACTURE AND PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Ceramic composites offer new opportunities for enhanced performance by applying principles of laminate design. These design techniques are very effective in improving the strength, toughness, corrosion, thermal and tribological properties of ceramic structure. The laminate ceramic composite design imposes new challenges in processing and manufacturing. The hot pressing of tape cast layers is most analogous to the lamination processes successfully used in polymer composites. This approach offers a high degree of control over the arrangement, and content of constituents in the final structure. The tribological performance of ceramic laminate designs is used to illustrate the potential for this approach.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of composite materials has been driven by the superior properties that can be developed by incorporating the filamentary forms into bulk forms. For polymer matrix composites the fibers carry a significant portion of the load, hence properties such as strength and stiffness are translated into materials properties by relatively simple relations. The matrix properties of polymer composites serve important but secondary functions of holding the reinforcements in place and assuring that the density and corrosion behavior are favorable. By contrast, the properties of metal composites are controlled more by matrix and interfacial properties although the strength and elastic properties of the reinforcements still provide the main contribution to strength and stiffness of the composite.

Ceramic composites provide a significant departure to the design philosophy of metal and polymer matrix composites. The stiffness of the reinforcement and the matrix are usually not very different, therefore, the fibers do not carry a large fraction of the load. The main function of the fiber is to provide toughness at room temperature and strength or creep resistance at high temperatures. The interfacial characteristics of ceramic composites play a major role in determining the strength, stiffness and fatigue properties.

Although the strengthening mechanisms and property modifications for each type of matrix is

different, the ability to tailor the material properties is the unifying concept for all composite materials.

2. DESIGN

The strength properties of ceramic composites are usually designed on the basis of microstructural control. Constituents are selected on the basis of thermal stability and processibility. Designs for improving the strength, reliability and fracture toughness of ceramics based on microstructural modification rely on the crack diverting characteristics of second phase particles, whiskers or fibers [1,2]. Macrostructural modifications are also used in ceramic composite design to induce surface compressive stresses [3]. Surface compressive stresses have been induced in ceramics by surface grinding of transformation-toughened monolithic ceramics such as ZrO_2 [4], quenching from high temperatures [5], coating with low expansion glazes [6], and applying low expansion layers by diffusion treatments [7]. Virkar et al. [8] fabricated three-layer composites by dry pressing powders to yield surface layers consisting of unstabilized ZrO_2 and an oxide (eg. MgO or Al_2O_3) and a core composition of the matrix oxide and stabilized ZrO_2 . On cooling, the unstabilized ZrO_2 transformed to monoclinic ZrO_2 and the outer surface expanded in dimension relative to the core producing a compressive residual stress on the surface.

Surface strengthening can also be achieved with the use of whisker reinforced laminates that combine increased toughening and surface compressive stresses into a ceramic structure. The use of continuous fibers for reinforcing ceramics would also be effective in laminate design since they permit better control of the orientation and placement in the matrix. Continuous fibers, however, have been limited to relatively low melting matrices such as glass and glass-ceramics [9,10]. For oxide matrix ceramics, silicon carbide is a commonly used reinforcement material [11]. The whisker form of SiC, is sufficiently stable to permit densification of many oxide matrix composites without its excessive deterioration. Although whiskers can be introduced easily into the matrix, the existing processing techniques for whisker reinforced ceramics permit very little control over their orientation and placement [12]. The application of tape casting techniques to the fabricated whisker reinforced composites circumvent these limitations and thus expand the design possibilities for whisker reinforced ceramic composites.

The concept of a laminated composite has been used effectively in the design of ceramic-matrix composites to achieve the high degree of strength through thermoelastic tailoring. Lamina, with discontinuous fibers produced by tape casting, are fabricated by stacking layers with specific compositions and orientations in a predetermined sequence to achieve desired mechanical or physical properties. Ceramic composite layer properties may be calculated using theoretical and semi-empirical micromechanics methods [13-16] from the constituent properties. By selection of the sequence of layer orientations and compositions, various elastic, thermoelastic, strength, physical, and chemical characteristics can be produced. Classical laminate plate theory, CLT, [17-18] has been used to accurately predict the elastic and thermoelastic properties of laminated composites from the layer properties. The design process for tailoring laminated ceramic composites is illustrated in Figure 1.

Examples of material designs that can make use of laminated-composite concepts for improved performance are illustrated in Figure 2. The magnitude of the surface compressive stress can be calculated from laminate theory. Figure 2(a) shows a laminate design intended to produce surface compressive stresses. In this design the layers toward the mid-plane gradually increase in coefficient of thermal expansion. The outer layers, containing increasing amounts of low-expansion whiskers generate compressive residual stresses as a result of the differential

Figure 1. Design approach for tailored laminated cermaic composites

Figure 2. Tailoring concepts in ceramic composite laminates

contraction during cooling after the high-temperature densification process. A major advantage of laminated-composite processing is that it provides the engineering flexibility to use innumerable material and property combinations that would be impossible with traditional methods involving thermal or chemical tempering. This concept also allows the use of non-equilibrium compositions for greater degree of stress profile variation. For instance, the depth and magnitude of the stress gradient can be independently controlled by selection of layer composition and properties. Maximizing the stress gradient by the introduction of a high-expansion material in the interior of the composite would be impossible by conventional chemical tempering, but is quite feasible by lamination.

Strengthening can also be achieved by rendering surface flaws ineffective through the introduction of a tougher ceramic layer below the surface (Figure 2b). This design mitigates surface damage in the outer layers by blunting the cracks when they reach the underlying toughened layer. This layer may contain either whiskers, a toughened ceramic, or metallic, particles. The use of a toughened ceramic layer as the outer layer would not be as effective since abrasion or impact could produce flaws through its entire depth, thus permitting the crack to propagate through the lower-toughness interior layers with minimum resistance.

In addition to increased strength and toughness, high-temperature wear resistance can be designed into a composite material by using an oxidation-resistant layer on the exterior surface (Figure 2c) and layers tailored for wear resistance and strength in the wear area. The core of the composite can be reinforced for improved toughness. A similar concept may be employed for a material designed as a high-temperature heat exchanger by substituting a strength layer for the wear layer and grading the interior layers for high thermal conductivity. Using composite laminate theory, a materials designer can tailor the grading to minimize the deleterious residual tensile stresses that are likely in such a construction.

Large differences in elastic and thermoelastic properties between matrix and whiskers permit the generation of significant residual stresses with the minimum use of whiskers. A material system which offers range of Young's moduli and thermal expansion coefficients are SiC_w-Al₂O₃. Laminates constructed from these materials can yield a wide range of composite properties. The constituent properties for these systems are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Constituent Material Properties for Laminated Composites

Property	Fiber SiC Whisker	Al ₂ O ₃ Matrix
Young's Modulus, MPa	586	380
Shear Modulus, MPa	290	156
Poisson's Ratio	0.19	0.33
Thermal Expansion Coefficient, 10 ⁻⁶ °C ⁻¹	3.96	7.92

3. PROCESSING

Laminated ceramic structures are fabricated by tape casting. This process is schematically shown in Figure 3. Individual tapes of 0.1 mm to 0.5 mm thick and up to 1 meter wide are deposited continuously onto a carrier tape under a spreading blade (Doctor Blade) from which it can be separated after drying. The tapes are cast from a formulated slurry comprised of a liquid, ceramic powder, organic polymer, plasticizer, and dispersant. These additives provide control over rheology during casting, flexibility during handling and shaping of the dried tape, and plasticity of the tape during consolidation and bonding. Laminates of a wide variety of architectures and compositional ranges can be produced by stacking the individual layers and then consolidating them. For more complex shapes, the flexible tapes can be wrapped, shaped, and formed on mandrels similar to those used in the polymer-composite industry. As much as 20 vol% of the unfired laminate is composed of organic additives that are removed by thermal decomposition or oxidation during the "binder- burnout" step prior to high temperature densification. The high temperature densification step is performed by hot pressing at 1750°C.

Figure 3. Processing sequence for laminated ceramic composites

4. PERFORMANCE

Laminates containing plies of different SiC whisker fiber fractions in an alumina matrix were examined for strength, toughness and wear resistance. Classical laminate plate theory was used to tailor SiC_w-Al₂O₃ for high strength, impact and wear resistance. Various ceramic materials including pure alumina and whisker reinforced alumina composites with 10, 20, 30 and 40 vol.% SiC were fabricated into plates from which four point bend and block-on-ring wear test specimens were prepared. Three hybrid designs, 20/10/20, 30/10/30 and 40/20/40, were also fabricated which have residual compressive stresses on the surface. The residual stress profiles for each of these designs are shown in Figure 4. A comparison of the flaw indented flexural strengths of monolithic, conventional composite, and a representative thermoelastically tailored ceramic composite laminate is shown in Figure 5. The measured strength of the unreinforced alumina is 120 MPa, which agrees with the calculated strength using accepted values of fracture toughness. Increasing the whisker content to 10 vol% raises the strength to 225 MPa in the

Figure 4. Residual stress profiles for thermoelastically tailored laminated ceramic composites

Figure 5. Bend strength of indentation-flawed, tape-cast SiC/alumina composites

longitudinal direction but to only 180 MPa in the transverse direction. These measured strength values are also in good agreement with values calculated from the flaw size, the residual stress, and the fracture toughness. Increasing the whisker content to 20 vol% raises the strength to 300 MPa in the longitudinal direction. The transverse strength does not increase as effectively as longitudinal strength with increased whisker content. A marked increase in longitudinal strength over the monolithic composites is produced by the thermoelastic tailoring. The favorable residual stresses in the 10/20/10 design resulted in a doubling of the fracture strength to 620 MPa.

To determine the wear characteristics of the laminated ceramic composites, block- on-ring tests

were performed at room temperature. All composite compositions were tested against Inconel 625 ring specimens with a contact pressure of 5.5 MPa and a sliding velocity of 9.2 m/s. Weight loss measurements in sliding distance intervals of 558 m, 837 m, 1116 m, 1395 m and 1674 m indicated that steady state wear was achieved within the first 588 m of sliding. The average wear rates for some of these compositions are shown in Figure 6. The wear rate decreases significantly with the addition of SiC whiskers to the alumina, but wear rate plateau is established between 10 to 30 Vol. % whiskers. The wear rates of the surface layers of the hybrid composites are similar to those of like composition among the single composition composites.

Figure 6. Wear behavior of laminated ceramic composites

The wear surfaces of the alumina indicate that intergranular fracture is responsible for the wear process. At 10 vol. % SiC composite the wear surface indicated that both intergranular and transgranular fracture processes are taking place during wear. With 40 vol. % SiC composite the fracture surface is predominantly transgranular. The high whisker content reduces the size of the grains and subsequently the wear debris size. The failure mechanism is by the transfer of a metal layer to the ceramic and its subsequent peeling off with adhered matrix and whisker particles. The wear rate appears to be controlled by the rate at which the transfer layer delaminates from the surface and the size of the wear particles.

5. SUMMARY

Laminated ceramic composites offer significant potential for tailoring materials to meet specific application requirements. These materials result in significant strength improvement over monolithic and conventional ceramic composites by combining the effects of whisker toughening and residual compressive surface stresses. Whisker reinforcement also produces a significant reduction of the wear rate of alumina matrix composites by limiting the size of the wear debris. Laminate designs can be produced which simultaneously improve both the strength, toughness and wear properties of the ceramic structure. Ceramic tape casting is currently the most suitable method for producing flexible preform lamina which can subsequently be stacked and bonded to form the laminated structures. Laminate design and fabrication techniques are ideally suited to producing special properties such as impact resistance and wear performance in ceramic composites.

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